

Influence of Family Background on Academic Performance of Students in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Emohua Local Government Area, Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined influence of family background on academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area, Rivers State. The researcher developed three (3) objectives, research questions and null hypotheses respectively that guided the conduct of the study. The research design used for the study was a descriptive research design. The population of the study consists of all SS I and SS II students in all Public Senior Secondary Schools in Emohua Local Government Area, Rivers State with the total population size of Eighteen Thousand, Two Hundred and Seventy (18,270). The sampling technique used for the study was multistage random sampling technique, with a sample size of 800 students, which was 400 students for SS I and another 400 for SS II students. The instrument used for the data collection was self structured questionnaire titled: Influence of Family Background on Academic Performance of Students Questionnaire, which was patterned towards 4-point rating scale. The instrument was validated by the research supervisor and measurement and evaluation experts from faculty of education, while the reliability of the instrument was achieved using split-half method to obtain a reliability coefficient value of 0.85. The data gathered were analyzed using weighted mean and standard deviation for the research questions, while the null hypotheses were tested using t-test statistical tool at 0.05 level of significant. Based on the data analysis, the findings of the study revealed that parental educational level, parental occupation level and parental level of income have significant influence on the students' academic performance. Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommends that: Parents should try as much as possible to increase the level of education, parents should try to get better occupation since it is not only going to help the family in times of feeding but it has a positive significant it influence students' academic performance and parents should try to diversify their sources of income to increase their income level.

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Key Words: Influence, Family Background, Academic Performance, Parental Occupation, Educational Level, Level of Income

INTRODUCTION

Family background or status refers to a person's position in a given group, society or culture as determined by wealth, occupation, education and social class. Amutabi (2013) discusses the impact of Family status on children's readiness for school. He asserts that the segregating nature of social class, ethnicity may well reduce the variety of enriching experiences thought to be prerequisite for creating readiness to learn among children. Social class and ethnicity, dictate neighborhood, housing, and access to resources that affect enrichment or deprivation as well as the acquisition of specific value systems. American Psychological Association, APA (2021) describes the relationship of family status and children's readiness for school across all Family groups; parents face major challenges when it comes to providing optimal care and education for their children. For families in poverty these challenges can be formidable.

So without parents not being ready to train their children, their performance in school might be discouraging due to individual differences. Even when some are being cared for properly, it is observed that they still could not cope with the system thereby leading to their failure or poor academic performance.

The family also provides an ascribed social class for its members. A child's initial social class is a very important variable in determining his/her educational attainment, selection of marital partner, place of residence, religious and political preferences, occupation and even life expectancy. As the saying goes "it is easier to climb the ladder of success if your parents own the ladder (Thompson & Hickey, 2022). The family is to a large extent where individuals acquire their specific social positions in society and parent socioeconomic background goes a long way in improving the child's life and welfare in all ramifications.

The school as an important agency for socialization is responsible for polishing the individuals for adult life. The major function of the school as an agent of socialization is the transmission of the cognitive aspect of culture (i.e. knowledge and ideas) from one generation to the other and preparation for adult roles. The school serves as both formal and informal socializing agent. Through its hidden curriculum it trains the individual to become useful to himself and society in general. The school provides conscious and systematic training among others.

Buchi (2015) further stated that family background which forms the subject of this study, includes housing condition, availability of reading materials and opportunities for intellectual development. Family factors, such as unsatisfactory housing condition may have a serious effect on educational achievement of a child. Large families, insufficient amenities, due to poor economic condition could distract the interest and attention of the Learner, which may affect the whole process. On the other hand, Buchi (2015) observed

that, children from poor families or those lacking those materials or amenities go to the school hoping to find the essential qualities lacking in their homes.

The family background of parents has its own consequences on educational achievement performance. Inability to pay regular school fees due to unfavourable economic situation can force some parents to send their children to substandard schools or even withdraw them from the school. Where such resources and facilitates are lacking, it is inevitable that the education of the child could be seriously affected in terms of their educational progress. In Poor family background parents cannot afford to provide all the material resources that are very important for educational advancement of their children in school. The absence or denial of such resources to their children is borne out of the necessity of their economic circumstances, not because they do not have similar aspiration like the high and middle Family parents who have these material recourses at their disposal (Blaks, 2016).

However, some factors like family size, parental educational levels, parental income levels and parental occupation, etc. have influenced the academic performance and achievement of the senior secondary students in Rivers State. It is against this background that the study seeks to investigate the relationship between parents' Family background and academic performance of senior secondary school students in Port Harcourt metropolis.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Family, parents and students' academic performance

The influence of parental Family variables on students' choice of career has been viewed by different scholars in different ways. According to Blair (2014) and Laosa (2021), both argued that Family background of parents is a direct drive to student educational aspiration. Blair (2014) further stressed this point by comparing the degree of educational aspirations between children from middle class and lower class homes, and observed that children from middle class are urged by their parents to aspire to higher level of educational achievement and also enter professional courses like Law, Engineering, Medicine, Accountancy etc. These children are even encouraged to read up to Ph.D level. Whereas on the contrary, children from low Family class parents may even be advised to forego education and encouraged to get involved in trading, learning of a skill or search for jobs that payment / salary may be so negligible. They also give them the impression that "it is not all that go to school get favoured.

However, Okeke and Agi (2017), believed that it is the material influence that has significant impact on the cognitive development of the child, and as some researchers have argued; Parcel and Menaghan, (2014), it makes sense to include separate variables for mother and father wherever possible. This is particularly true, in the view of Asuka (2019). More especially in Rivers State, a student from a lower class home who may be residing in water fronts and ghettos of Port Harcourt environs seem to be more interested in education than those living in Government Residential Areas (G.R.A.). The idea behind their seriousness is to make sure they leave their waterfront residence, break the chain of poverty in their lives and be classified in the future as middle class income people. But children

from middle class socioeconomic parents who live in Government Reserved Areas with all their flamboyance have monitoring of the school experience etc. Praise has a positive impact on colleges and universities grades and school monitoring has a positive effect on class performance.

A research conducted by Stephenson (2014) on the factors that influence occupational preference in America found that there is a positive correlation between parents' social status and the categories of job chosen by their children. Contributing to this view, Osueke (2017), carried out a study on the "influence of urban, rural and Family background on the pattern of vocational choice among post-primary pupils in Enugu area. He found that nearly a third, 96 out of 319 students indicated that they were influenced in their choice of career by their mother, father, brother or sisters. He also found that this influence varied with the Family background of their parents and sex in which girls were more influenced than boys. In other words, the higher the socioeconomic status of the parents, the greater the influence they exert on their children's choice of career.

Some notable Nigerians have also conducted researches on the effect of parents' income level on children's choice of career. According to Ojo (2015), parents' income level affects their children's choice of career because in most cases, children from high income parents receive not only secondary school education but they also attend the best secondary schools where well qualified teachers and well equipped laboratories for science subjects are available. On the other hand, a large number of children from poor parents usually attend teacher training colleges because their parents cannot afford secondary school education.

Today, with the phasing out of teachers' training colleges, the dichotomy is created between public schools which are poorly funded by government and private schools which are established and better funded by individuals. The children of the poor attend public schools because they are less expensive but lack effective learning whereas the children of the high income earners attend good schools mostly private schools which are better equipped with learning facilities with high cost.

Subscribing to the view that parents have a great influence on their children's choice of career, Durojaiye (2018) carried out a study on choice of career among students of the International Secondary School, Ibadan. He observed that 95.5 percent of the students chose professional career such as university lecture, Medicine, Engineering, Accountancy, Law etc. 63.3 percent of the students sampled chose the professional careers for academic reasons. The study also showed that parents were very influential in their children's choice of career 42.3 percent of the fathers and 38.3 percent of the mothers wanted their children to engage in professional occupations.

Evidence of close links between vocational development and socioeconomic background has been presented by various studies. Ginzberg (2021) found that boys from high-income families tend to assume that they would go to college even at quite early age. Later when they enter the realistic choice stage, he observed that they restricted their choices to

occupations of a professional executive kind. On the other hand, he found that boys from low income families tend to think in terms of skilled jobs which will offer a higher rate of remuneration than their fathers received. One of the major constraints of vocational development of boys from lower-income families is their modest level of aspirations.

Carter in Ipaye (2016) stated that the solid working class families are those which more or less accept the standards upheld in the wider society but are rather easy going and inclined to take life as it comes. The home environment does little to encourage the children to aspire to anything other than the type of jobs held by their parents and immediate neighbors. Children from low socioeconomic status homes aspire to occupations at a higher level than their parents, they find no suitable role models with the family and few family activities relate to their aspirations, while children from high Family background homes who are only equipped for occupations at a lower level than their parents find themselves similarly disadvantaged. Such children tend to depend more on influences outside the homes.

Besides, family members from various studies revealed that they are of considerable importance and often parents head the list as those seen as exerting helpful influence. Children from many homes rely on their parents on vocational matters. In other words, the parents represent a credible information source and therefore any advice they offer is considered very important.

Boyd and Coop (2019) maintain that there is a relationship between Family background and occupational achievement. Some studies revealed that upper class boys tend to aspire to higher level occupation than do those from lower strata. Empey (2012) found students from higher Family levels aspire to higher level occupations than students from less advantaged backgrounds. In his contribution Rosenberg in Pryor (2016) contends that the father's economic background contributes greatly to the child's career choice. He found that the higher the income of the father, the higher the income the child wishes to obtain. Researchers conducted by American National opinion centre clearly stage that as good percentage of students from high status family background studied disciplines such as law and medicine. Family class therefore influences educational attainment which in turns influences occupational and career opportunities and development.

At this point, an understanding of the Nigerian child in relation to his vocational needs is necessary. A consideration of conception of the child in the traditional and modern Nigerian society is also of immense importance. In the preliterate and pre-industrial Nigeria, the child's horizons were largely shaped by his family. His position in life was likely to be same as his father. If his father was an "Osu" or cult slave or a traditionalist, he would likely live his own life as any of the above. If on the other hand the father was a medicine man. We would likely to be a medicine man. He was a part of his family production enterprise throughout his life. With the introduction of public education in modern times a radical change has emerged in the scene. This change has affected the traditional role of the family, it altered the family function as a self perpetuating economic unit and as a training ground.

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With the introduction of trade and industry, children have begun to be occupationally mobile and less dependent on their family.

Income Level of Parents on Students Academic Performance

The income level of parents is also viewed from the perspective of the Family characteristic. This includes father's education, father's occupation and occasionally, mother's education (Ogbu, 2021). A student deciding to make a choice for any vocation or career may embark on such initiative by reflecting one's mind or perception on one's parental income level. Parental income is believed by some quarters to be one of the driving factors, which may compel a student to choose a career.

From the above, Briggs (2014), suggested that due to changes in family structure, increased labour force participation by women, and increased rates of single parent families headed by women suggests that mother's occupation should be included in future conceptualizations of family class background due to its significant effect on educational attainment. Subsequent studies by Ginbury and Rebican (2018) in supporting the concept of Harman and Hanson (2016), opine that children from low income family are greatly affected by income which is a manifestation of their modest level of aspirations. The reason is that their environment is so absurd that it refuses to instill motivation for appropriate transaction of interest, aptitude and capacity into realizable occupational career.

The reasons for the above findings are far-fetched. This implies such that such an influence is made possible because children from well to do homes are gingered to take up professional courses since their parents are ready to provide them the much needed educational materials and instructional resources to update and enhance their educational aspirations. Whereas those from the low income are not privileged to benefit from such an induced environment, which have enabled them translate, develop and actualize their potentialities.

However, the researcher is of the view that children of today often times disregard, their parents level of income when taking up any career or vocation. Well, it is agreed that finance is indispensable in enhancing one's life goal, it is possible that one can take-up a career or course by utilizing the limited resources available to him to actualize one's purpose in life.

Vocational development and occupational level of Parent and student academic performance

According to Agi (2012), Vocational development is the process of change due to acquisition of certain skills, knowledge, ideas, and attitudes about the world of work which is not static but progressive. It involves process of building up of values, skills, attitudes and so on. It is so the process of shaping, moulding and orienting the individual towards the world of work. To this end, Agi (2012) observed that emphasis of work was on choice, but choice is static because it takes place at a time. Now the emphasis is not on choice, it is how the child grows up, make up or build up his ideas, spirit and values about work.

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1. Vocational development predicts what an individual is capable of doing.
2. It makes individual make rational choice which given in rate satisfaction.
3. It makes children appreciate dignity of labor.
4. It makes children know meaning of work.

Consequently, subsequent studies by Denga (2015) and Owen (2019) relate to the fact that parents get involved in the occupational choice, which could be fulfilled by their children. In other words, this explains that parents see their children as a second chance whose future is to compensate for their occupational frustrations and disappointments. Thus the researcher is of the opinion that a child choice of career in our present day society most especially if the existing occupational value grant job security, prestige, high wage and opportunity advancement (Osuji 2015), which in other words must be in conformity with the Social value of the present society. Hence, students should be taught now some of the ways in which the things they learn in school may help them later in life.

Parents' family background as Predictor of Secondary School Students' Academic Performance

Despite the fact that the development of any nation depends largely on the quality of education of her citizen, the academic performance of most Nigerian youth in secondary schools is decreasing. This has become a major concern of education stake-holders and researchers. Imogie (2012) drew attention to the public outcries concerning the low quality of education in Nigeria. Ige (2017) confirmed that students who took the Senior School Certificate Examinations in Ekiti State performed poorly between 2005 and 2007. Ugoji (2018) lamented that students' academic performance is declining because they are confronted with so many school and nonschool related demands and responsibilities. Abdu-Raheem (2020) agreed that the problem of students' under-achievement has been an educational issue since the early 80s. Abdu-Raheem (2020) also confirmed through the data collected from Ekiti State Ministry of Education that only 26.9% of students that sat for Junior Secondary School Examinations for five academic sessions in Social Studies passed at credit level. Hassan (2013) examined and listed the causes of poor academic performance among secondary school students. Some of the causes are low intellectual ability, poor study habits, low achievement motivation, lack of vocational goals, low self-confidence, low Family background of the family, poor family structure and anxiety. Different factors such as the child's intelligence, state of health, motivation, anxiety, availability of suitable learning environment, adequacy of educational infrastructure, may influence students' academic performance positively or negatively (Eweniyi, 2015). They identified low motivational orientation, low self-esteem/self-efficacy, emotional problems, poor study habits, poor teacher consultation and poor interpersonal relationships as some of the causes. Fayemi (2021) also highlighted inadequate funding, poor teaching methodology, infrastructural decay, low morale among the teachers, indiscipline among teachers and students as factors responsible for the students' failure in national examinations. Adegbite (2014) noted that most Nigerian students at every level of education sponsor their education

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by engaging in various kinds of works like prostitution, keke driver, daily pay labourer, security guard, recharge card selling, fuel attendant and casual worker.

Statement of the Problem

The notion that the standard of education has fallen, has generated a lot of arguments among scholars and educationists. Teachers, government and students are often blamed for this phenomenon without investigating other factors that could hinder high standard of education. Every child in school performs differently in terms of academics, which may either be positive or negative. Experience has shown that among the secondary school students there are variations in the type of schools' children attend. Peters (2020) observed that most parents seem to be more interested in the feeding and clothing of their children than in their educational progress. Some parents do not care about teaching and encouraging their children at home. They believe that the school teachers will do everything.

It has been observed that many students do not pass well in both internal and external examinations such as West African School Certificate (WASC), National Examination Council (NECO) and Junior Secondary School Certificate (JSSC). Obanya (2014), Ebenuwa-Okoh (2020), and Atanda & Jaiyeoba (2021) noted that some of the factors responsible for the low performance of students in schools are low Family background of parents and lack of seriousness on the part of the students. There is poor students' academic performance and achievement in public senior secondary schools as a result of parental Family background or background. These status includes; parental level of education, parental occupation, the family population or size and parental level of income. Some scholars like, Uba, (2016), Oti, (2018) and Owen (2019) have actually carried out studies on the relationship between parental Family background and students' career choice in Rivers State. In this case, emphases were not given to the students' academic performance which has necessitated this research or study. In the light of this, this study intends to examine the influence of family background on academic performance of students' in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to examine the influence of family background on academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives are among others to:

1. find out the extent to which parental educational level influences academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State.
2. examine the extent to which parental occupation influence academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State.

3. determine the extent to which the parental level of income influence academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent does parental educational level influences academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State?
2. To what extent does parental occupation influence academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State?
3. To what extent does parental level of income influence academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The study was guided by the following null hypotheses:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of SS I and SS II students on the extent parental educational level influences academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of SS I and SS II students on the extent parental occupation influence academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State
3. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of SS I and SS II students on the extent parental level of income influence academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

In carrying out this research, the researcher employed descriptive survey design. It attempts to describe or document current conditions or attitudes, that is, to explain what exists at the moment. Descriptive survey design is a research method which focuses on a representative sample derived from the entire population. This design was adopted because of its ability to ensure a representative outlook and provide a sample approach to the study of opinion, attitudes and values of individuals. The population of the study consists of all Senior Secondary 1 (SS1) and Senior Secondary 2 (SS2) students in all public senior secondary schools in Rivers State with a total population of 18,270 students made up of 8,900 SS1 students and 9,370 SS2 students (Rivers State Ministry of Education, 2020). The sample size of this study is 800 students (400 SS1 and 400 SS2 students) fixed using the Taro Yamene sample size formula given as $S = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$, where S = sample size, N =

population of the study, and e = significance level of the study. To obtain 400 students each for SS1 and SS2 students, the Taro Yamene formula was applied to the sub-populations of SS1 and SS2. The sampling technique used was the multistage sampling technique. The instrument that was used for data collection in the study was a self-structured questionnaire titled “Influence of Family Background on Academic Performance of Students Questionnaire” (IFBAPSQ), which was divided into two parts. The first part is the demographic information about the respondents, while the second part consists of respondents’ responses on the subject matter. It was patterned on a modified 4 – point likert scale of Very High Extent (VHE) – 4 points, High Extent (HE) – 3 points, Low Extent (LE) – 2 points, and Very Low Extent (VLE) – 1 point. To ensure the face and content validity of the instrument, the questionnaire was given to the research supervisor and two other experts in the Measurement and Evaluation, all in the Faculty of Education, Rivers State University for professional touch and corrections. All the corrections made were strictly incorporated in the final draft of the questionnaire. To ascertain the reliability of the instrument, the researcher adopted split-half method. The instrument was administered once to 20 SS1 and 20 SS2 students in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State in a Local Government Area not used for the study. The two sets of data from the administration of the instrument were analysed for consistency using the Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation analysis and a reliability coefficient of 0.85 was obtained. Eight hundred (800) copies of the questionnaire were administered on the SS1 and SS2 students with the help of two research assistants who were recruited and trained for the study. The researcher retrieved the executed copies of the instrument immediately after completion. The data collected was analysed using weighted mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions. The criterion decision rule is that any mean score that was from 2.50 and above was accepted, while the mean score that was less than 2.50 was rejected. The null hypotheses were tested using t-test statistical tool at 0.05 level of significance with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), Version 23.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: To what extent does parental educational level influences academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Table 1 Mean and standard deviation responses on the extent parental educational level influences academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State

S/ No	Questionnaire Items	SS I Students =400			SS II Students =400		
		Mean \bar{X}	SD	Remark	Mean \bar{X}	SD	Remark
1.	Educated parents ensure that their students or children are educated no matter the cost or involvement.	2.90	0.57	High Extent	2.95	0.57	High Extent
2.	Educated parents promote their children’s education by providing their needs academically.	2.95	0.57	High Extent	2.99	0.58	High Extent
3.	Illiterate parents have little or no concern about their children education thereby affecting their academic performance.	2.90	0.57	High Extent	2.95	0.57	High Extent
4.	Most educated parents do not allow their children to learn or acquire skills or entrepreneurship.	3.05	0.58	High Extent	3.10	0.59	High Extent
5.	Some educated parents normally train some of their children to take after their profession.	2.85	0.56	High Extent	2.98	0.57	High Extent
	Grand Mean	2.93	1.71		2.99	1.73	High Extent

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The analysis in table 1 indicated that the respondents agreed that educated parents ensure that their students or children are educated no matter the cost or involvement. The respondents still accepted the view that educated parents promote their children’s education by providing their needs academically. The analysis also showed that the respondents accepted that Illiterate parents have little or no concern about their children education thereby affecting their academic performance. It was still observed from the analysis that the respondents accepted that most educated parents do not allow their children to learn or acquire skills or entrepreneurship. The table also revealed that the respondents agreed that some educated parents normally train some of their children to take after their profession.

Research Question 2: To what extent does parental occupation influence academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation responses on the extent parental occupation influence academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State

S/ No	Questionnaire Items	SS I Students =400			SS II Students =400		
		Mean \bar{X}	SD	Remark	Mean \bar{X}	SD	Remark
6.	Most lawyers (learned men) like their children to take after their profession thereby providing everything for them to improve their academic performance.	2.90	0.57	High Extent	2.95	0.57	High Extent
7.	Children or students' vocational development are mainly trace from their parental occupational background.	2.85	0.56	High Extent	2.95	0.57	High Extent
8.	Some medical students have parents that are medical doctors thereby encouraging them in the profession to improve their academic performance.	2.60	0.54	High Extent	2.80	0.56	High Extent
9.	Parental occupation helps in shaping, moulding and orienting their children on their own profession thereby promoting their academic performance.	2.90	0.5	High Extent	2.99	0.53	High Extent
10.	Parents see their children as a second chance whose future is to compensate for their occupational frustrations and disappointment thereby encouraging their children to perform well academically.	2.55	0.53	High Extent	2.65	0.54	High Extent
Grand Mean		2.76	1.66		2.87	1.69	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The analysis in table 2 above revealed that the respondents accepted the point that most lawyers (learned men) like their children to take after their profession thereby providing everything for them to improve their academic performance. The analysis still showed that the respondents agreed the view that children or students' vocational development are mainly trace from their parental occupational background. It was also observed from the table that the respondents accepted that some medical students have parents that are medical doctors thereby encouraging them in the profession to improve their academic performance.

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The analysis in the table still indicated that the respondents agreed the point that parental occupation helps in shaping, moulding and orienting their children on their own profession thereby promoting their academic performance. The table also showed that the respondents accepted the view that parents see their children as a second chance whose future is to compensate for their occupational frustrations and disappointment thereby encouraging their children to perform well academically.

Research Question 3: To what extent does parental level of income influence academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State?

Table 3 Mean and standard deviation responses on the extent parental level of income influence academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State

S/ No	Questionnaire Items	SS I Students =400			SS II Students =400		
		Mean \bar{X}	SD	Remark	Mean \bar{X}	SD	Remark
11.	Students in their education or academics consider the financial level of their parents thereby improving their academic performance.	2.55	0.53	High Extent	2.65	0.54	High Extent
14.	Rich parents provide everything for their children education thereby promoting their academic performance.	2.90	0.57	High Extent	2.95	0.57	High Extent
12.	Rich parents like training their parents to any level of education no matter the cost thereby promoting their academic performance.	2.85	0.56	High Extent	2.98	0.57	High Extent
13.	Children from well to do home or family are gingered to take professional courses since their parents are ready to provide all the necessary materials.	3.05	0.58	High Extent	3.10	0.59	High Extent
15.	Some children from low income family are not privilege to have all the reading or school materials thereby affecting their academic performance.	2.90	0.57	High Extent	2.95	0.57	High Extent
Grand Mean		2.85	1.69		2.93	1.71	

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The analysis in table 3 above showed that the respondents accepted the view that students in their education or academics consider the financial level of their parents thereby improving their academic performance. The table still revealed that the respondents agreed that rich parents provide everything for their children education thereby promoting their academic performance. It was also observed from the table that the respondents supported the point that Rich parents like training their parents to any level of education no matter the cost thereby promoting their academic performance. The analysis still indicated that Children from well to do home or family are gingered to take professional courses since their parents are ready to provide all the necessary materials. The analysis revealed that some children from low income family are not privilege to have all the reading or school materials thereby affecting their academic performance.

Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of SS I and SS II students on the extent parental educational level influences academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Table 4: Z-test Analysis of significant difference in the mean ratings of SS I and SS II students on the extent parental educational level influences academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Status	N	Mean \bar{X}	Standard Deviation	Df	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
SS I Students	400	2.93	1.71	798	1.24	1.96	Accepted
SS II Students	400	2.99	1.73				

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The analysis on Table 4 indicates that the z-cal of 1.24 is less than the z-crit of 1.96. Therefore, the calculated z-ratio is not statistically significant at a 0.05 level of significance since it is greater than the given critical value of z-ratio. Therefore, the hypothesis 1 is thus accepted and the conclusion is that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of SS I and SS II students on the extent parental educational level influences academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of SS I and SS II students on the extent parental occupation influence academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Table 6: Z-test Analysis of significant difference in the mean ratings of SS I and SS II students on the extent parental occupation influence academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Status	N	Mean \bar{X}	Standard Deviation	Df.	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
SS I Students	400	2.76	1.66	798	0.22	1.96	Accepted
SS II Students	400	2.87	1.69				

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The analysis on Table 5 revealed that the z-cal of 0.22 is less than the z-crit of 1.96. Therefore, the calculated z-ratio is not statistically significant at a 0.05 level of significance since it is greater than the given critical value of z-ratio. Therefore, the hypothesis 2 is thus accepted and the conclusion is that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of SS I and SS II students on the extent parental occupation influence academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of SS I and SS II students on the extent parental level of income influence academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Table 6: Z-test Analysis of significant difference in the mean ratings of SS I and SS II students on the extent parental level of income influence academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Status	N	Mean \bar{X}	Standard Deviation	Df.	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
SS I Students	400	2.85	1.69	798	1.29	1.96	Accepted
SS II Students	400	2.93	1.71				

Source: Field Survey, 2024

The analysis on table 6 shows that the z-cal of 1.29 is less than the z-crit of 1.96. Therefore, the calculated z-ratio is not statistically significant at a 0.05 level of significance since it is greater than the given critical value of z-ratio. Therefore, the hypothesis 3 is thus accepted and the conclusion is that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of SS I and SS II students on the extent parental level of income influence academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Discussion of Findings

The finding in research question one: To what extent does parental educational level influences academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua

Local Government Area of Rivers State indicated that parental educational level influences academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State. The study showed that educated parents ensure that students or children are educated no matter the cost or involvement. The respondents still accepted the view that educated parents promote their children's education by providing their needs academically. The analysis also showed that the respondents accepted the point that Illiterate parents have little or no concern about their children education thereby affecting their academic performance. This study is in line with the view of Henslin (2016), who observed that most educated parents do not allow their children to learn or acquire skills or entrepreneurship. The analysis also revealed that the respondents agreed the fact that some educated parents normally train some of their children to take after their profession.

The result of research question two: To what extent does parental occupation influence academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State reveals that parental occupation influences academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State. The study revealed that most lawyers (learned men) like their children to take after their profession thereby providing everything for them to improve their academic performance. The findings still showed that children or students' vocational development are mainly trace from their parental occupational background. This study is in line with Oti (2018) who observed that some medical students have parents that are medical doctors thereby encouraging them in the profession to improve their academic performance. The analysis indicated that parental occupation helps in shaping, moulding and orienting their children on their own profession thereby promoting their academic performance. The findings also showed that parents see their children as a second chance whose future is to compensate for their occupational frustrations and disappointment thereby encouraging their children to perform well academically.

The result of research question three: To what extent does parental level of income influence academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State showed that parental level of income influence academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State. The study is in line with Henslin (2016) who observed that students in their education or academics consider the financial level of their parents thereby improving their academic performance. The study still revealed that rich parents provide everything for their children education thereby promoting their academic performance. It was also observed from the table that the respondents supported the point that rich parents like training their children to any level of education no matter the cost thereby promoting their academic performance. The findings also indicated that children from well to do home or family are gingered to take professional courses since their parents are ready to provide all the necessary materials. The study revealed that some children from

low income family are not privilege to have all the reading or school materials thereby affecting their academic performance.

Conclusion

The influence of family background on academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State cannot be overemphasized. However, the study concludes that parents' family size and educational attainment level of parents have significant influence on the academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools. The study also deduced that there is a positive and significant influence on income levels of parents, parents' occupation on academic performance of students in public senior secondary schools. The researcher still concludes that parental status provide the first learning opportunity for the students and that family background of parents is a direct drive to students'

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are hereby put forward to ensure that this study achieved its objectives:

1. Parents should try as much as possible to increase the level of education. This is because higher level of educational attainment of parents has positive relationship with the students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools.
2. Parents should try as much as possible to get better occupation since it is not only going to help the family in times of feeding but it has a positive significant relationship on the students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis.
3. Parents should try to diversify their sources of income to increase their income level because the parental income level of the students has positive and significant relationship on the students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

REFERENCES

- Abdu-Rabeem, M. (2020). "Influence of age, financial status and gender on academic performance among undergraduates", *Journal of Psychology*, 1(2), 99-103.
- Animasalum, T. (2013). "*Suggested ways of improving the performance of students in Biology*". Ado-Ekiti: Akolawole Printers.
- Asuka, A. M. (2019). "The effects of parental Family background on academic performance of students in selected schools in Edu Local Government of Kwara State", *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*. 2 (7), 230-239.

- Atanda, I. & Jaiyeoba, N. (2011). "Factors affecting students' quality of academic performance: A case of Secondary School level", *Journal of Quality and Technology Management* 7 (2),1-14.
- Baridam, D.C. (2019). *Introduction to Research Methods*. Lagos: Longman Publishers.
- Blaks, N. (2016). Factors underlying Occupational preference; *West African Journal of Education* 8 (3), 9-15
- Briggs, R. (2014). *Guidance and counseling for handling adolescent and youth*, Ibadan: African Education Press.
- Buchi, M.A. (2015). *Foundation of guidance and counseling for colleges and universities*, Enugu, Academic. Publishing Co.
- Cobbeld, C. (2016). "Collapse of family values in Nigeria: Social Studies Education to the Rescue", *International Journal of Special and General Education* 3, 185-190.
- Denga, S. (2015). *Guidance and counseling for handling adolescent and youth*. Ibadan: African Education Press.
- Douglas, M. H. (2019). *Schooling in capitalist America: educational reforms and the conditions of economic life*. New York: Macmillan Press limited.DCI.
- Duncan, M. (2019). School Occupation, Culture and family; The Impact of parental Schooling of a parent child Relationship. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 74 (6), 16-25
- Henslin, R. (2016). "Class and schools using social economic and educational reforms to close the white and black achievement gap", *Economic Policy Institute*, USA.
- Hurlock, M.R. (2021). "*Family determinants of academic performance of secondary school students in Nigeria*". University of Ilorin: An unpublished B. Ed project.
- Hurlock, O. (2021). *Sociology, themes and perspectives*. New Delhi: Oxford University Press.
- Ibe, K. (2003). "Education summit", <http://allafrica.comstories>. Hassan, T. (1983), "Psychosocial predictors of academic achievement", *Psychology for Everyday Living*, 2(2), 155-169.
- Igwe, S. (2013). "Deaf children: their right to education through sign language", *Journal of International, Journal of Special and General Education*. 3,103-107.
- Kendal, J. (2013). "Impact of parents' Family background on university students' academic performance", *Ife Journal of Educational Studies*, 7(1), 31-39.
- Majoribank, A. M. (2016). Impact of school subject on the choice of occupations and professions. *West African Journal of Education* 15 (1), 20-36

- Margrave, G. (2021). *Theories of job satisfaction and job performance, an overview and critique (focus on the teaching profession.,)* Lagos: Longman Publishers.
- Menaghan, S. & Parcel, G. (2014). “*The dynamics of secondary education: A synthesis of studies in four states of the federation*”, Washington D.C : The World Bank.
- Mwiria, W. (2017). “Family background and academic achievement trajectories from childhood to adolescence”, *Canadian Journal of Education* 32 (3):558-590.
- Ofoegbu, A. (2016). Educational and occupational prestige in Nigerian Secondary School Students, *West African Journal of Education*.17 (3), 5
- Ogbu, A. (2021). “Effects of family structure and parenthood on academic performance of Nigerian university students”, *Stud Home Comm. Sci.* 2(2), 121-124.
- Ojo, R. (2015). “Class and schools using social economic and educational reforms to close the white and black achievement gap”, *Economic Policy Institute*, USA.
- Olufemi, O. D. & Adewuyi, R. J. (2021). *Introduction to curriculum studies*. Port Harcourt: Pre Joe Publishers.
- Onwuasonya, M. (2018). “The effects of poverty on academic achievement”, *Journal of Educational Research and Review*. 6 (7): 522-527.
- Osueke, Y. (2017). “Family background and students’ academic performance”, <http://socyberty.com/education/family-background-and-student-academic-performance>.
- Oti, M. R. (2018). *Sociology, themes and perspectives*: Mew Delhi, Oxford University Press.
- Owen, O.E. (2019), “The influence of poverty on students’ behavior and academic achievement”, *International Journal of Educational Research* 2(1): 151-160.
- Peretomode, C. (2018), “Relative effects of problem-solving and discussion methods on secondary school students’ academic achievement in social studies”, Unpublished Ph. D Thesis, Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State University.
- Petters, P. (2020), “Academic interactions among classroom peers: across country comparison using TIMSS”, *Applied Economics*, 39 (12),1531-1544.
- Peters, P. (2019). Impact of school subject on the choice of occupations and professions. *Journal of Educational Focus*. 6(3), 98-125.
- Pryor, B. E. (2016). “The influence of poverty on students’ behavior and academic achievement”, *International Journal of Educational Research* 2(1), 151-160.
- Randall, G.O. (2015). *Principles and practice of education*, Nigeria Longman.

- Sheldon, U. (2013). "Etiological factors and effects of street working behaviour among Nigerian youth", *Journal of Social Problem, School of Arts and Social Science, F.C.E. (special) Oyo*, 2, 1.
- Shertzer, J.O. & Stone, R. (2018). *Introduction to curriculum studies*. Port Harcourt: Pre Joe Publishers.
- Stephenson, J.I. (2014). "Predictive validity of the Junior Secondary School Certificate Examinations (JSSCE) for Senior Secondary School Certificate Examinations (SSCE) in Ekiti State", *Journal of Educational Focus*. 2(1) 142-147.
- Uba, P.C. (2016). *Understanding the child, a psychological perspective*. Onitsha: Cape International Ltd.
- Udegbo, I. (2017). *Research methods: An introduction*. Benin City, University of Benin.
- Ugoji, N. (2018). "Factors affecting students' quality of academic performance: A case of Secondary School level", *Journal of Quality and Technology Management* 7 (2):1-14.
- Wedge, V.& Possess, B. (2018). *Sociology of education*. Lagos: Longman group Ltd.
- Wilkins, B. G. (2013). Man power planning and occupational choice in Nigeria. *West African journal of education*. 8(3), 16-27